

REMOVAL INK EFFICIENCY OF FLEXOGRAPHIC PRINTED PAPER PACKAGING MADE FROM DIFFERENT ALTERNATIVE PLANTS

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Abstract: *Paper is one of the most common solid waste items, and recycling it is relatively inexpensive and straightforward. By limiting the flow of waste papers to landfills, recycling waste papers helps to reduce pollution. Recycled and reused waste papers are significant low-cost fibre resources (raw materials) for the pulp and paper industry. In the recycling of recovered paper, enzymes have been proposed as an environmentally kind alternative to standard chemical deinking. Enzymes have the potential to minimize chemical demand while also lowering process costs and environmental impact. The production of paper for packaging is increasingly focused on using alternative biomass as a source of pulp. Agro-waste, urban green cuts all pose a potential source of alternative fibres. In our research, we have investigated three different paper samples made from tomato stems (120g/m²), Robinia pseudo acacia (120g/m²) and miscanthus (125g/m²) printed with water-based flexo inks used in paper packaging. We performed two parallel deinking tests according to ISO 21331:2020 and ISO ISO 21933:2020, and one alternative also involved an enzymatic pretreatment of the samples. The mechanical properties of all papers showed an increase after enzymatic treatment, while the traditional chemical treatment resulted in better optical properties, but still with a large colour shade offset due to remaining ink particles.*

Keywords: alternative fibres, deinking, enzymes, flexography

1 INTRODUCTION

Wastepaper recycling is both environmentally and economically beneficial since it reduces the consumption of forest-based raw materials and the amount of old paper in landfills (Makinen et al., 2013 & Kumar et al., 2017). Because most energy is consumed during pulping of virgin fibre raw materials, recycling waste paper uses 28–60 per cent less energy than virgin fibre papermaking. An efficient wastepaper collection system can achieve a high recycling rate. Europe has the highest recycling rate of paper and paperboard at 71.7 per cent, while North America, Asia, and Latin America have the lowest rates (EPRC, 2020). On the other hand, the constant rise of the price of wood pulp and the need for a more circular economy drives biomass sourcing to other alternative sources. In addition to increasing the use of the number of fibres in papermaking, fibres are also very sought in composite manufacturing, where fibres are added to synthetic polymer materials (plastics). This application reduces the consumption of non-biodegradable plastics and improves the toughness and strength of plastic materials. Also, more than half of the woody biomass in the EU is used for energy sourcing.

Alternative sources have been already used for print and packaging applications (Karlovits et al., 2021). While studies on these alternative fibre papers are well known for several biomass types (Adriansee and Morsink, 2007, Neclaw et al., 2010, Azeez 2018; Abd El-Sayed, El-Sakhawy, and El-Sakhawy, (2020)), their deinking efficiency is not. For example, most of the deinking studies were done on hydrophobic inks used in offset printing (mainly in newspaper printing), but in packaging printing, hydrophilic water-based inks are used for paper packaging printing. The dispersion of the hydrophilic inks into submicron particles has been shown to result in drastically reduced ink separation by flotation and redeposition of the ink onto the fibre. Conventional flotation is currently the dominant separation method for inks during paper recycling, and this type of flotation has an optimal particle size range of about 30-250 microns. As mentioned, this is ideal for the inks used for offset printing but is not suitable for submicron hydrophilic ink particles. Other forms of flotation for removing smaller particles are significantly more expensive and tend to drastically reduce the loss of paper fibre during the separation (Lee, 2014). The utilization of enzymes in the deinking process reduces deinking chemicals while also lowering the discharge of hazardous substances into the process water. Bio-deinking by enzymes is an environmentally friendly process that improves pulp and paper properties and reduces chemical consumption during waste paper recycling.

Enzymatic deinking results in cost reductions, efficient ink particle separation, and improved strength qualities (Gao et al., 2018 & Hasanin et al., 2020). According to Bajpai (2014), enzymes have been proposed as an environmentally beneficial alternative to conventional deinking chemicals. Enzymes have the potential to minimize chemical demand while also lowering process costs and environmental impact. Cellulases, pectinases, amylases, lipases, esterases, and laccases are examples of these enzymes. Because flexographic and other hydrophilic inks cannot be removed by flotation, a high proportion of hydrophilic inks poses a severe problem for the deinking process. Optimization of pulping conditions, including the employment of several types of enzymes, is one such problem. Existing solutions, however, have not been able to eliminate the reduction of pigmented inks on recycled paper deinking (Hsieh, 2012). Lee et al. (2013) were also unsuccessful in their research since they used a qualitative approach.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our study compared deinking processes by using classic deinking chemicals and specific enzymes (cellulase, enzyme mixture). We investigated which treatment was more efficient by determining the optical and mechanical properties of the deinked papers. For substrates, we have used three types of papers produced on a pilot paper machine from agro-waste residues (tomato stems), urban green cut residue (acacia) and dedicated grow non-woody crop miscanthus. The papers have been produced at the Pulp and paper Institute, and their properties are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of treated and untreated Miscanthus, Tomato and Robinia pseudo acacia paper

Parameter	Miscanthus	Black Locust (<i>Robinia pseudoaccacia</i>)	Tomato stem
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	125	120	115
<i>Hardwood pulp (%)</i>	0	30	40
<i>Softwood pulp (%)</i>	33	30	40
<i>Freenes of pulp (SR)</i>	25	25	27
<i>Alternative fibers (%)</i>	67	40	20
<i>Cationic starch (%)</i>	0.75	1	1
<i>Fillers (%)</i>	0	10	5
<i>Surface sizing (%)</i>	2	3,5	4

2. 1 Sample printing

Samples were printed with water-based flexographic inks (Doneck) on a laboratory flexo printer IGT F1 with the printing form thickness of 1.7 mm HD Flexo was used and with 0.6 m/s printing speed, printing force of 120N and anilox force of 60 N (the anilox had 80L/cm) which results in 8.5ml ink transfer on m²). We have used just blue ink (to more easily control the colour coordinates as the paper has a distinct colour shade). The used inks had a viscosity of 20s measured with ISO Cup 4. All samples due to the same printing conditions had the same transferred ink quantity.

2. 2 Deinking process

Samples were merged and cut to pieces of 2x2 cm. Dry matter, according to the standard EN 14346: 2007, was also determined. Each sample weighed 75 g of absolutely dry matter. The deinking process was carried out by slightly modified standards ISO 21331:2020: ISO 21892:2020 and ISO 21993:2020.

Chemical deinking process

During the experiment, we used the following chemicals: sodium hydroxide (NaOH), oleic acid, sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). 100 mL of H₂O₂ was added into the solution of chemicals (400 mL), and the mixture was diluted with water to a volume of 1500 mL. 75 g of absolutely dry sample was added to the mixture of chemicals during constant stirring at 3000 rpm in a thermostat spreader (T = 45 °C, time of mixing 20 minutes). The temperature was maintained by using a water bath. Once the dissolution was completed, the mixture was stabilized in a water bath for 60 minutes at a constant temperature of 45 °C. Based on the standard, the recommended pH value was during pulping is 9,5 ±0,5 and during flotation > 7,5. The next step was the flotation of the previously dissolved sample, which took place in a flotation cell in the presence of water (18 L). After the flotation process, laboratory paper sheets were prepared.

Enzymatic deinking process

75 g of absolutely dry sample was added to 1500 mL of water and solution of chemicals during constant stirring at 3000 rpm in a thermostat spreader (T = 45 °C, time of mixing 5 minutes). The temperature was maintained by using a water bath. After 5 minutes of mixing the sample and chemicals, we were added 100 mL of enzyme dilution we pre-prepared (98 mL of water was added 2 ml of the enzyme, at temperature 55 °C) and let it work for 30 min at 55 °C.

2. 3 Analysis of optical and mechanical properties

ISO brightness and CIE L*a*b* coordinates of laboratory paper sheets were measured using WinPaper Elrepho 450 X Datacolor spectrophotometer. CIE00 delta E formula was used to determine the quality of the deinking process as the starting papers are not bleached and have distinct colour shades. The mechanical properties of the deinked samples were determined on the deinked laboratory sheets obtained after different treatments: grammage (ISO 536:2012), thickness (ISO 534:2011), specific volume (ISO 534:2011), tear index (ISO 1974:2012), elongation at break (ISO 1924- 2:2008) and tensile index (ISO 1924-2:2008), ISO brightness (ISO 2470-1) and colour differences (ISO 11664:2014). The properties of the laboratory paper sheets were determined at the temperature of 23 °C and 50% relative humidity.

3 RESULTS

The mechanical properties of the deinked samples are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of treated and untreated Miscanthus, Tomato stem and pseudo-Accacia paper

	<i>Before deinking</i>	<i>After deinking</i>	<i>Before enzymatic deinking</i>	<i>After enzymatic deinking</i>
MISCANTHUS				
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	43.9	43.8	43.9	40.08
<i>Thickness (um)</i>	149.7	143	136.0	149.0
<i>Specific volume (cm²/g)</i>	3.41	3.26	3.09	3.72
<i>Tear index (mPam²/g)</i>	3.12	3.28	3.26	3.57
<i>Tensile index (Nm/g)</i>	45.43	47.58	50.90	53.72
<i>Tensile lenght (m)</i>	4631	4850	5188	5476
TOMATO				
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	39.9	41.7	45.7	44.3
<i>Thickness (um)</i>	156	144	153.8	138
<i>Specific volume (cm²/g)</i>	3.91	3.45	3.37	3.12
<i>Tear index (mPam²/g)</i>	2.42	2.43	2.54	2.82
<i>Tensile index (Nm/g)</i>	33.0	34.59	38.21	38.95
<i>Tensile length (m)</i>	3364	3526	3895	3971
ACCACIA				
<i>Grammage (g/m²)</i>	43.2	42.7	40.5	34.3
<i>Thickness (um)</i>	150.8	137	136	136.5
<i>Specific volume (cm²/g)</i>	3.49	3.21	3.36	3.98
<i>Tear index (mPam²/g)</i>	1.04	1.06	1.16	1.12
<i>Tensile index (Nm/g)</i>	20.40	20.78	20.70	20.93
<i>Tensile length (m)</i>	2079	2118	2110	2125

Based on the mechanical properties results of the paper, an improvement with the addition of the enzyme is observed. Comparing enzymatic deinking and without enzyme shows that the enzyme has favourable properties to improve the following parameters: tear index, tensile index, and tensile length. As the papers made from alternative fibre sources have a distinct colour shade with low ISO whiteness as they are not bleached to have a more sustainable paper production, we have measured the effect of the deinking with also focus on the colour differentiation deinked papers. The results are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1: ISO Whiteness %

Figure 2: Colour difference ΔE_{00}

From Figure 1. We can observe that the chemical deinking and the enzymatic pretreatment have increased the overall ISO Brightness of the samples in comparison with the base paper, which is an average effect due to the presence of hydrogen peroxide. The use of the enzymes lowered the effect of the chemical bleaching, resulting in lower values for all types of papers, as shown in Figure 2. We can see that all the paper, regardless of the enzymatic pretreatment or with the pure chemical and floatation deinking, had very high observable colour differences (over $\Delta E_{00} 6$), indicating that after deinking, the paper shades are entirely completely different than the starting one. Using just one type of inks (blue) affected the CIE b^* colour coordinate, where the highest differences were measured. As miscanthus had a very distinct yellowish starting point, the highest colour difference of the paper's colour shade was confirmed due to the lowering of the higher b^* value to lower (more neutral ones). This effect was partly due to the bleaching effect and partly by the remaining flexo ink particles, which was noticeable that the deinked papers had a blueish colour shade.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The deinking study of the three papers developed and made from alternative sources intended for packaging purposes where the print is expected showed that the enzymatic pretreatment is beneficial regarding the mechanical properties of the paper obtained after deinking. Based on the results, we can see that the paper has slightly better properties after enzymatic deinking in terms of mechanical properties. Even though we did not achieve the expected results in removing flexo inks, a good result is that the quality of the paper remains the same or even improved. The efficacy of the enzyme was not satisfactory. We suggest optimization of the deinking process, especially in terms of time and activation of the enzyme, and at the same time, other types of enzymes should be tested. We believe that the enzyme also depends on the type of paper, for us specifically, because it is an alternative source of cellulose (lignocellulosic biomass) and contains impurities, which may affect the activity and efficiency of the enzyme.

On the other hand, the optical properties were lower with the enzymatic pretreatment. The conventional treatment increased the ISO whiteness of the unbleached papers but opened up a particular challenge in reusing the unbleached alternative fibre papers in the packaging printing. The significant colour differences between the base papers made from alternative sources can cause problems with colour reproduction due to a large colour shade change which inevitably influences colour reproduction and standardization efforts.

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